

A new way of Reaching consumers: the Role of Marketing Related Mobile Factors on the Consumers' Acceptance of Multichannel Mobile Marketing

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Abstract

This research investigates factors that may affect the level of acceptance of mobile marketing and determines if there is a relationship between these factors and level of acceptance of mobile marketing. It separately investigates the most influential factors affecting the level of acceptance. This research was to investigate as well if there were differences in the readiness of undergraduate students regarding acceptance and factors leading to acceptance in terms of gender, age, education and place. The research depends upon a sample of undergraduate students studying in universities. The researcher employed statistical techniques such as descriptive, correlation analysis, linear multiple regression, one-way Anova, and the post hoc test. The main findings from this research are that factors affecting acceptance were related to the level of acceptance of mobile marketing in the research field of reality. There is a significant difference between undergraduate students regarding factors affecting acceptance of mobile marketing; also there is a significant difference between undergraduate students regarding their readiness of acceptance in terms of some demographic characteristics.

Keywords: Mobile Marketing Acceptance ,Advertising, Applications ,perceived Usefulness,Quick Response Code,Short Messages Service,Location Based Services

1.Introduction

For As technology continues to advance, communication channels will continue to grow and change. Since its launch, the internet has conquered all the aspects of human life. The way people access information, share information, communicate, and interact with each other has been drastically modified. In addition, the internet contributed erasing geographical barriers and reducing the factors of space and time.

Driven by the fast changing technological developments, today's business environment has viewed increased mobility and an obvious increase in the use of mobile devices by consumers. In light of these developments, mobile marketing industry has grown significantly and is set to continue growing [50].

The high global penetration of mobile communication devices is only one indicator of the high potential of marketing via mobile. Moreover, the specific characteristics of the mobile phone allow for marketing measures not realizable by the use of other media.

Thus, marketing via mobile supports both the marketers and consumers because marketers can increase their client base as they can access several consumers of different identities and various geographical areas, while consumers will also have a wide range of products choices .Also marketing via mobile is still at its opening but has

an immense potential to grow as the environment experiences further technological advancements[20]. So, the purpose of this study is to gain more understanding about the factors of the mobile marketing acceptance, these factors are drawn from Two theoretical areas (the technology acceptance model (TAM) and uses and gratifications theory) which study the interaction between users and technology, and have been widely applied in the marketing literature to explain individual behavior related to the adoption and usage of technology.

2. Background information

Some scholars define mobile marketing as the use of mobile to personal information, provide others with specific locations, one-to-one communication, and for entertainment.[16]

The Mobile Marketing Association (MMA), a global spearhead in stimulating mobile marketing through mobile devices labels mobile marketing as, “the usage of wireless media as an integrated content delivery and direct response vehicle within a cross media marketing communication program”

In this study, basing on the shared features of mobile media, mobile marketing is defined as, “any marketing activity steered through a recognized network to which consumers are frequently connected via a personal mobile device”[8].

Mobile marketing is a set of marketing practices that use wireless mobile technologies and networks to create personalized and interactive communication between an organization and its target audience, resulting in value creation for both parties[46].

The definition of mobile marketing by[51], which is the following: “mobile marketing is the two-way or multi-way communication and promotion of an offer between a firm and its customers using a mobile medium, device or technology”. Since smartphones are found to be highly relevant for mobile marketing nowadays[54].

Marketing via mobile is the use of wireless media as a delivery of an integrated content and a direct interaction means in a cross-media marketing communication program and in a world where everything is mobile, more and more people talk about the any area anywhere, anytime, any device, any channel, any product, any event and any me [47].

Marketing via mobile works as a kind of framework, a glue between all the other media (points of sale, events, TV, radio outdoor, online etc.). It is the center of all other programs. A campaign cannot be done only by Marketing via mobile, it supports the others by its main advantage which is the interactivity according to the [48].

The mobile marketing Association recently redefined marketing via mobile as "a set of practices that enables organizations to communicate and engage their audience in an interactive manner through any mobile device or network". Sometimes mobile marketing is called wireless marketing[48].

Marketing via mobile influences consumer acceptance because of its unique features of being permission, incentives and location-based which makes it possible to reduce consumer irritation, to create consumer interest, to identify and satisfy individual consumer needs, and to send messages to specific locations, and this increases the chances of consumer acceptance [52]. Marketing via mobiles acceptance is defined as “an individual consumer’s propensity to accept new technologies and use them in a way that they will find useful” [26].

Therefore, as consumers are increasingly exposed to marketing via mobiles, their acceptance is also increasing[5].

conceptualized consumer acceptance of marketing via mobile as the degree to which consumers engage in mobile marketing activities [55] also indicates that consumer are likely to accept marketing via mobile activities because it provides information to consumers on a regular basis and help marketers to showcase their products to consumers and this ultimately induces consumer interest.

Therefore, as consumers are increasingly exposed to marketing via mobile, their acceptance is also increasing as Mobile phones represent a medium that, up to now in many markets, has been used primarily for voice and data communications rather than for marketing activities. Findings from more recent research suggesting that acceptance of mobile marketing is, in part, influenced by consumers’ acceptance of the mobile medium itself [18].

Mobile marketing acceptance has been described as “the power of one's intention to carry out a specified behavior” [50]. Consumer acceptance lies upon three main previous **key drivers of mobile marketing**, in the following approaches:

-Technology

Marketing campaigns need to be developed in line with latest technology that is readily accessible to the consumer. In case a marketing campaign utilizes modern technology, another campaign needs to be established to target the demographics lacking some access to such technology.

-Marketer Attitudes

Marketing campaigns need to be developed giving priority to the consumers. In case a campaign utilizes principles inapplicable to the targeted mobile consumer, it will become unsuccessful. As a result, marketing agencies must establish a balance between ideals developed by traditional media, along with an understanding of the modern mobile market.

-Content

According to [31], if a marketing campaign is to make use of content, it needs to provide the consumers with a sense of value. This incentive-driven marketing strategy allows marketers to target consumers, without a negative feedback. According to [25], even with such collaboration from other interested parties, building effective mobile marketing still largely relies upon the issues of trust as well as privacy.

“Since the mobile is a very personal device that allows an individual to be accessed virtually any time and anywhere, mobile advertising must be more personalized and may take different forms” [50].

[51]state that this construct narrates to respondents' receptiveness as well as some intentions to take on activities such as reception of products or information linked to marketing as well as promotional offers on their mobile phone devices.

If mobile application designers and service providers want to get more benefits, as well as more market share, they should make an understanding of some reasons behind the consumer's intentions in using and adopting new services. Mobile service providers should realize the needs and desires of users and try to give them satisfaction through delivering optimized in addition to customized services. Marketing distribution channels can be regarded as the method which is used for enterprises placing products into the market for consumers to use. As mobile phone devices become the new primary means for consumers to interact with their favorites offerings, the trend in which established brands are interacting with their consumers as well prospects is still undergoing some rapid changes.

Brands are catching on the growing significance of mobile phones. Marketers need to develop some clear as well as defined tactics aimed at driving some awareness to attract the interest of their customer base and prospects. Perceived usefulness can be considered as the major factor influencing the adoption of information and communication technology oriented services. Perceived usefulness can be defined as the point in the evoked set of one's mind which gives perception about certain system that, using that system would lead to enhanced performance [2]. Mobile marketing's first goal is to present information to the final user. Furthermore, different information is available using phone devices.

The majority of consumers are seeking direct communication to receive information. “Innovativeness” is the degree to which a consumer is relatively earlier in adopting new ideas than others of his social group. Each individual has a specific tendency to accept or reject innovation.

The risk associated with mobile marketing is mainly perceived as one of data security. New media services users tend to have concerns about data manipulation, unauthorized data access, and unwanted tracking of usage patterns. Another security issue concerns consumers' privacy.

Some of the channels that marketers can consider using in distributing their products to consumers using the mobile platform are: short message services ,multi-media services (SMS/ MMS) ,mobile web ,mobile applications (mobile apps) ,mobile ads ,mobile tagging and quick response (QR) codes.

Using mobile marketing opens the door for people to access abundant content, Mobile marketing allows people to access more content than do traditional and email channels. Furthermore, the probability of accessing different content relies heavily on expectations, experience, and mobile devices[5]. Studies find that information privacy content obtained by mobile users is a concern that can be mitigated by other factors.

3. Research reasoning:

As marketing via mobile is a promising strategy, several facts can explain why marketing via mobile works as a kind of framework, a glue between all the other media (points of sale, events, TV, radio outdoor, online etc.).

This strategy recorded an 82.8 % growth rate in advertising through mobiles during 2012, with 7.5 billion users in 2014 that reached 8.5 billion users by the end of 2016 [56].

Moreover, marketing via mobile spending in Middle East and North Africa reached 85 million and 50 million euro in 2012 and 2013 respectively. The Egyptian ministry of communication reported that from October 2015 to November 2015 the mobile subscription increased from 93.13 million to 93.67 million at monthly change rate 0.58. At the same interval time period, mobile penetration increased from 106.72% to 107.17% at annual change rate 0.45 [39].

According to[42], the number of smart phone users is forecast to reach 2.08 billion in 2016, and the number of users worldwide is expected to pass the five billion mark by 2019. So, it's no wonder that mobile advertising will represent 72% of all US digital ad spending by 2019.

By the end of 2020, the world will have over 55 million mobile devices, opening up huge possibilities and new types of applications for their users. Mobile technologies can be used for other tasks besides communication. They can allow consumers to acquire products and services, when they want and where they are[23].

From these indicators the researcher came to the result that while mobile marketing is an increasingly important promotional vehicle with some significant advantages over traditional media, many marketers have failed to use mobile marketing effectively. This poor performance is evidenced by high bounce rates, low completion rates, and poor average sales in comparison to laptop and desktop-based promotions. So the research problem can be expressed in the following statement: "Weak readiness of smart phone users to accept the marketing offers provided by the mobile in comparison to laptop and desktop-based promotions".

4-Research objectives:

This study aims mainly to reach the following objectives: To identify the type and strength of the relationship between marketing via mobile and factors affecting consumers' acceptance, Determine factors that have the most influential effect on marketing via mobiles, Determine if there are any differences among undergraduate students' perception regarding factors affecting consumers' acceptance of mobile marketing in terms of their demographic characteristics (gender, age, education).

5-Research Importance:

The results of such research would help mobile advertisers design various interactive tools to increase accepting mobile advertising on web sites and webpages, also would allow marketers to directly send pictures or videos of products and to answer customer questions and queries.

So, this research can help both of them to effectively communicate with each other's. This quantitative study extends the academic knowledge of marketing via mobiles by testing whether some factors influence consumers' readiness to Accept Marketing via mobiles some but not others. This research will give mobile advertisers information regarding critical variables that have influenced a consumer to accept an advertisement via mobiles, to increase this acceptance and therefore reduce wastage of media spending. The study will provide useful information to marketers who will be able to access several consumers at any time and establish close relations with consumers and this helps to influence purchase, also helps consumers to access to wide range of diverse information about varied products and services.

6-Research Methodology:

The present research adopts the quantitative research method as this research is considered descriptive in nature.

Research hypotheses :H1: There is no significant relationship between consumer's readiness factors (providing information, risk avoidance, customer innovativeness, perceived usefulness, accessing content) and marketing via mobile acceptance. H2: Consumer's readiness factors have the same impact on marketing via mobile acceptance.H3: Marketing via mobile acceptance not significantly differs according to consumer's demographics (age, gender, education and place).

Mobile Marketing studies:

There have been extensive international researches that examine and analyze the importance and influence of the factors affecting consumers' readiness to accept marketing via mobiles. These studies provide the theoretical basis for this study.[16] identified that attitude, social norm and perceived value are the critical success factors of marketing via mobile acceptance while [19] found that the critical factors for the acceptance are attitude, perceived value, and perceived enjoyment.

[7]mentioned that perceived expressiveness, normative pressure, ease of use, perceived usefulness, perceived enjoyment, and behavioral control are the success factors of marketing via mobile acceptance, while[14]pointed out that the factors are risk avoidance, permission to interact, attitude, usage properties, and innovativeness.

the most influential factors for marketing via mobile acceptance are attitude, ease of use, and perceived enjoyment [6]considered that amount of information, Perceived usefulness, Ease of use, perceived Credibility are the critical success factors for marketing via mobile acceptance; however it showed that risk acceptance, providing information, accessing content ,personal attachment are the most critical success factors of marketing via mobile acceptance.

On the other hand[22]found that perceived usefulness, perceived credibility, social influence are the key drivers of marketing via mobile acceptance, while according to [23]the main antecedents of marketing via mobiles acceptance are perceived usefulness, perceived value, enjoyment, trust, perceived cost, attitude, personal attachment and self-harmony.

[47]suggested that accessing content, sharing content, providing information, risk acceptance, personal attachment are considered valuable motivations that lead to marketing via mobile acceptance. However, [10]demonstrated that permission to interact, usage properties, privacy, personal attachment, attitude& innovativeness are the key motivators of marketing via mobile acceptance. [11]illustrated that perceived usefulness, subjective norm, attitude, ease of use, family & friends, perceived enjoyment, perceived image are factors that lead to marketing via mobile acceptance. while [30]pointed out that risk degree, accessing Content, sharing content, personal attachment, providing information are leading factors to mobile marketing acceptance.

Furthermore it was concluded that attitude, irritation, perceived usefulness, entertainment are the most antecedents factors of marketing via mobile acceptance. On the other hand, [20]indicates that antecedents of marketing via mobile acceptance are providing information, sharing content and accessing content. According to [5]the key indicators of marketing via mobile acceptance are providing information, accessing content, personal attachment, perceived value and sharing content.

While [3]found that ease of use, personal attachment, perceived usefulness, risk avoidance, innovativeness, and attitude are the main indicators marketing via mobile acceptance.

In addition to , [4]investigate that the major factors of marketing via mobile acceptance are providing information, enjoyment, privacy, brand familiarity, personalization, subjective norms, incentives, consumer control, and clarity. [2]identified that the most major success factor of mobile marketing acceptance are ease of use, privacy, providing information, accessing content, sharing content, and risk acceptance.

[13]found that entertainment, personalization, incentives, irritation, attitude, and credibility are considered as the most influential factors of marketing via mobile acceptance. Finally, according to [35]the key factors of marketing via mobiles acceptance are entertainment, irritation, personalization, attitude, incentive, and credibility.

The target population for this research was basically composed of young Egyptian mobile users represented in undergraduate students. The sample method utilized was non- probability sampling. The sample was divided disproportionately between the two universities because the disparity between their sizes was put into consideration.

The researcher started to distribute the questionnaire translated into Arabic among respondents by using an on-line survey to collect data as the research topic is highly relevant to the medium used, and it enabled quick and accurate gathering of survey information.

The instrument of collecting data for this study was a questionnaire that consisted of three major parts. (A); marketing via mobiles acceptance. (B); factors affecting the acceptance.(C); asked for personal information. The answers could be given by using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1= strongly disagree to, 5= strongly agree.

For the Dependent variable :

Marketing via mobile acceptance measured by using a scale derived from [29][30]& [5]14 items scale. Each item will be measured using a five-point likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

For the Independent variables:

These variables will be measured using scales, the scales and items that used in this survey are drawn from existing sources. These measures were chosen as these are the most common scales used in previous literature.

Reliability and validity tests were performed on the research instrument using the SPSS Cronbach Alpha test. The results came back with alpha coefficients of more than (0.7) and total Validity is (0.859) which indicated high reliability and validity. The results of reliability analysis revealed that most of item-total correlations were above 0.30 for all items in the questionnaire. On the other hand, alpha coefficients were more than 0.60 for all scales used in the questionnaire which is acceptable and assure the internal consistency between items in the questionnaire. Also, the study results come back with the total coefficient of stability (alpha cronbach) for the total questioner is (0.739) and total Validity is (0.859) which indicated high reliability and validity.

Research Hypothesis :

H01:"There is no significant relationship between consumer's readiness factors and marketing via mobile acceptance". The results indicated in Table (1) are as follows:-**H1.1:** There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and providing information. The correlation coefficient (0.464) it was statistical significance at level 0.01.

H1.2: There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and accessing content. The correlation coefficient (0.431) it was statistical significance at level 0.01.

H1.3: There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and Risk avoidance. The correlation coefficient (0.201) it was statistical significance at level 0.01.

H1.4: There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and Customer innovation. The correlation coefficient (0.373) it was statistical significance at level 0.01.

H1.5: There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and Perceived usefulness. The correlation coefficient (0.446) it was statistical significance at level 0.01.

Table (1) correlation between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and both of (providing information, accessing content, Risk avoidance ,Customer innovation, Perceived usefulness).

Items	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
providing information	0.464**	0.000
accessing content	0.431**	0.000
Risk avoidance	0.201**	0.000
Customer innovation	0.373**	0.000
Perceived usefulness	0.446**	0.000

Source: statistical results .

H02: "Consumer's readiness factors have the same impact on marketing via mobile acceptance". Table (3) shows the values of independent variables coefficient and found that the model variables are statistically significant at a confidence level (0.95).

As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that the independent variables have real value coefficients different from zero is accepted and they have areal impact on mobile marketing acceptance.

As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that Consumer's readiness factors have not the same impact on marketing via mobile acceptance.

Table (2) Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.840	.707	.698	7.19434

a. Predictors: (Constant), perceived usefulness, Risk avoidance, providing information, customer innovation , accessing content.

Source: statistical results.

From table (2) it is clear that total correlation (R) was (0.840) This correlation is medium, the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R Square) was (0.698) that mean the independent variables explain 69.8% of any changes in Mobile Marketing Acceptance, the regression model is statistically significant when the F-test was (42.387) it significant at level (0.01).

Table (3) the values of independent variables coefficient.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.921	3.704		3.488	.001
	providing information	0.494	.057	.272	8.667	.000
	accessing content	0.292	.061	.173	4.787	.000
	Risk avoidance	0.197	.048	.091	4.104	.000
	customer innovation	0.371	.081	.097	4.580	.000
	perceived usefulness	0.237	.064	.117	3.703	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Mobile Marketing Acceptance

The previous table (3) shows the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted; that the independent variables affect Mobile Marketing Acceptance.

H03: Marketing via mobile acceptance not significantly differs according to consumer's demographics (age, gender, education and place).

H3.1: Marketing via mobile acceptance not significantly differs according to consumer's education (governmental sector, nongovernmental sector). table (4) showed that: There are significant differences between the governmental sector and the nongovernmental sector in the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of the nongovernmental sector. The average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance was 56.71 degrees, with Standard deviation about 8.19 degrees, while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the governmental sector was 52.13, with Standard deviation about 8.38 There was an increase in the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance about 4.58 in favor of the nongovernmental sector. This increase was significant Where the value of "T" about 5.435, which have a statistical significance at level 0.01.

Table (4) Results of a significant test of the differences between the respondent's governmental sector and the nongovernmental sector in readiness to Accept Marketing via Mobiles.

Items	Sector	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-test	Sig. (2-tailed)
Mobile Marketing Acceptance	nongovernmental	187	56.7112	8.18549	.59858	5.435	0.000
	Governmental	200	52.1300	8.37999	.59255		

Source: statistical results

H3.2: Marketing via mobile acceptance not significantly differs according to consumer's gender (male, female).

Table (5) showed that: There are Non-significant differences between the male and the female in the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of male. The average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance was 54.54 degrees, with Standard deviation about 8.58 degrees, while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the female was 54.03, with Standard deviation about 8.45 There was an increase in the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance about 0.51 in favor of the male. This increase was Non-significant Where the value of "T" about 0.570.

Table (5) Results of a significant test of the differences between the Male and the Female in readiness to Accept Marketing via Mobiles.

	sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-test	Sig. (2-tailed)
Mobile Marketing Acceptance	Male	239	54.5397	8.68094	.56152	0.570	.569
	Female	148	54.0270	8.45391	.69491		

Source: statistical results

H3.3: Marketing via mobile acceptance not significantly differs according to consumer's ages. Table (6) showed that there are significant differences between ages of the respondents in the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of ages 19-20, the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance was 60.06 degrees, with Standard deviation was about 6.19 degrees. While the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the (21-22) was 53.92, with Standard deviation about 7.91, while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the 23-24 was 53.58, with Standard deviation about 7.74, while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the 17-18 was 48.94, with Standard deviation about 10.58, There was significant increase in the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance favor of ages 23-24, Where the value of "F" about 20.349 which have a statistical significance at level 0.01. Table (6) Results of a significant test of the differences between the ages of the respondents in readiness to Accept Marketing via Mobiles.

Items	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	f	Sig
Mobile Marketing Acceptance	17-18	51	48.9412	10.58378	1.48203	20.349	.000
	19-20	72	60.0556	6.19834	.73048		
	21-22	192	53.9219	7.91375	.57113		
	23-24	72	53.5833	7.74733	.91303		
	Total	387	54.3437	8.58745	.43652		

Source: statistical results

H3.4: Marketing via mobile acceptance not significantly differs according to consumer's Places of residence (Capital, center, city and village). Table (7) Results of a significant test of the differences between the respondent's Places of residence in Readiness to Accept Marketing via Mobiles.

Items	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	f	Sig
Mobile Marketing Acceptance	Village	122	52.5738	9.36312	.84770	4.641	.003
	City	94	53.9043	7.84400	.80905		
	Center	80	54.6625	8.30120	.92810		
	Capital	91	56.8901	7.95327	.83373		
	Total	387	54.3437	8.58745	.43652		

Source: statistical results.

Table (7) showed that there are significant differences between Place of residence in the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of Capital, The average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance was 56.89 degrees, with Standard deviation about 7.95 degrees, while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the center was 54.68, with Standard deviation about 8.30, while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the city was 53.90, with Standard deviation about 7.84. while the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in the village was 52.57, with

Standard deviation about 9.36, There was significant increase in the average of the Mobile Marketing Acceptance favor of Capital, where the value of "F" about 4.641 which have a statistical significance at level 0.01.

7-Conclusions:

The main conclusion is that all the research constructs (providing information, customer innovativeness, accessing content, perceived usefulness, risk avoidance) have a significant influence on mobile marketing acceptance.

Another key finding from the research is that there are Non-significant differences between the male and the female in the Mobile Marketing Acceptance but there is differences in favor of male .This is further revealed as most respondents preferred to receive only one marketing message per day whilst a sizeable proportion did not want to receive mobile marketing notifications at all as they consider the messages annoying.

The mobile advertising industry impacts a consumer every time a new message is received by the customer. This is especially relevant since mobile is such a personal medium and is always present with the customer. Unlike other media an advertising message on mobile is to be received first even if the consumer does not read or pay attention to the message.

There is a positive relationship between the acceptance of mobile marketing and the factors (Providing information, risk avoidance, customer innovativeness, perceived usefulness, accessing content, demographic differences). There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and accessing content There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and risk avoidance. There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and customer innovativeness. There is a positive relationship between Mobile Marketing Acceptance and perceived usefulness. Consumer's readiness factors have different impact on marketing via mobile acceptance. Marketing via mobile acceptance significantly differs according to consumer's demographics (age, gender, education and place). There are significant differences between the students of governmental sector and the nongovernmental sector toward Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of the nongovernmental sectors. There are not significant differences between the male and the female toward Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of male. There are significant differences between ages of the respondents toward Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of ages (19-20). There are significant differences between Places of residence in the Mobile Marketing Acceptance in favor of Capital.

Marketers must take care that if users feel their privacy has been violated they will avoid the ads risk, they must state clearly how their information collected and used and keep them up to date with privacy changes. Mobile advertisers must design various interactive tools to increase accepting mobile advertising on web sites and webpages, also would allow they should directly send pictures or videos of products and to answer customer questions and queries so; both of them can effectively communicate with each other's.

Mobile advertisers must build trust in their information they introduce and collected through ads, make sure of the sufficiency of their information and confirm that their ads provide a true picture of their products. Advertisers should make their ads useful for users as much as they can, to make their ads related to the users personality, matching with their values, opinion and attitudes.

Mobile marketers must take into consideration the nature of mobile. It is a place of social interaction more than a place of commercial exchange. So, they should deliver a small number of highly targeted ads instead of a large number of advertisements .

Marketers should track their conversion rates and understand their market better, because mobile device users often send their feedback immediately. Risk perception in the context of mobile marketing mainly results from the fear of data misuse and the reception of unwanted mobile marketing messages. Marketers should definitely be advised against using impersonalized mass messages for communicating advertising content.

8- For Further research:

- It would be useful to conduct an experimental study that directly measures actual acceptance readiness through mobile.
- A comprehensive study will be needed to examining the effect of different acceptance reasons.
- Further research is also needed on the concept of permission marketing.
- Finally, cross-cultural studies in the domain of mobile marketing are still quite scarce.

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